

INVESTIGATIONS ON THE REDUCTION OF MERCURIC CHLORIDE BY OXALIC ACID INDUCED BY POTASSIUM PERSULPHATE

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The kinetics of the reduction of mercuric chloride has been studied at various temperatures and concentrations of the reactants. The reaction is found to progress through various zones such as : (i) period of induction, (ii) normal reaction of zero order, (iii) auto-catalysis, (iv) auto-inhibition and (v) reversible reaction. A tentative mathematical expression, based on the chain mechanism of the reaction, has been derived for the velocity of reduction of mercuric chloride. Sodium acetate up to a limiting concentration is found to accelerate the reduction tremendously, but it produces an inhibiting influence when in large excess.

The activation of oxalic acid in presence of oxidising agents, such as potassium permanganate, potassium persulphate, etc., manifested in the ready reduction of mercuric chloride to mercurous state, was first observed by Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 690; this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 203) and subsequently studied by Oberhauser *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1928, 61, 521; *Annalen*, 1929, 470, 111) and others (Wieland and Zilg, *Annalen*, 1937, 530, 257; Thunberg, *Arch. Physiol.*, 1928, 54, 6; Abel, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1937, 43, 629). Weiss (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, Disc., 1947, 2, 188) suggested a chain mechanism based on the formation of $C_2O_4^-$ radical in the oxidation of oxalic acid by potassium permanganate to explain the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid-permanganate system. Ladbury and Cullis (*Chem. Rev.*, 1958, 58, 403) and Waters (*Quart. Reports*, 1959) have discussed the postulation of free radicals, such as CO_2^- , and their relevant role in similar mechanisms of redox reactions. Prasad and Bhattacharya (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 3) studied this reaction from the view point of the concentration effect of the inductor (potassium permanganate) on the induction period and extent of reduction of mercuric chloride.

The induced reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid in presence of potassium persulphate was quantitatively studied by Dhar (*loc. cit.*) who observed the relationship between the amount of inductor used and the amount of calomel formed. The present investigation includes the kinetics of the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid induced by potassium persulphate, and an attempt has been made to explain the mechanism of this reduction.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure was the same as described in a subsequent part (under publication). For studying the kinetics, the reaction was allowed to progress for different intervals of time in different conical flasks under identical conditions of temperature and concentrations of the reactants. The amount of calomel precipitated in each flask at desired intervals of time was filtered off through a double-walled funnel containing ice-cold water in between its walls. This prevented further reduction of mercuric chloride even during filtration. The precipitate was then washed and estimated by a standard potassium iodate solution (Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", pp. 361-367). The influence of nitrogen and sodium acetate on the kinetics of the reduction of mercuric chloride was also studied. The zero-order velocity constant was calculated by the expression :

$$k_0 = dc/dt$$

where dc is the amount of mercurous chloride (in terms of KIO_3) formed during an interval dt .

Influence of Temperature

The reaction was studied at different temperatures. The results obtained at 50° are summarised in Table I and the influence of temperature on this reaction is represented by Fig. 1.

TABLE I

$(K_2S_2O_8)_0 = (H_2C_2O_4)_0 = (HgCl_2)_0 = 0.02 M$. Temp. = 50° . Period of induction = 15.0 mins.

Time (t).	Volume of KIO_3 .	Average C.	$k_0 \times 10^2$.
0 min.	0.0 c.c.	20.0	..
60	0.6	19.7	10.00
120	1.2	19.1	10.00
180	1.8	18.5	10.00
240	2.4	17.9	10.00
300	3.0	17.3	10.00
360	3.6	16.7	10.00
420	5.2	15.6	26.66
480	5.8	14.5	10.00
540	6.3	13.95	8.33
600	4.8	14.45	-25.00

From Table I and Fig. 1, it is observed that at 50° the reaction after a period of induction slowly develops, exhibiting zero-order for 360 mins. After this period the velocity abruptly increases up to 420 mins., and then diminishes gradually. At 600 mins. the value of k_0 is found to be negative, suggesting the reversibility of the reaction. These observations lead to the

FIG. 1

conclusion that the whole course of the reaction consists of five zones: (i) Period of induction, (ii) normal reaction, (iii) auto-catalysis, (iv) auto-inhibition and (v) reversible reaction, and may be governed by a chain mechanism.

From Fig. 1 it may be seen that an increase of temperature increases the velocity of the overall reaction and affects its various zones. The periods of induction and normal velocity decrease, while the rate of auto-catalysis increases and its period is shifted towards earlier intervals. Both, the period of auto-inhibition and the stage of reversibility, set in earlier. The temperature coefficient of the reaction during its normal course is found to be 5.9 between 45° and 55° and 5.4 between 50° and 60°. The corresponding activation energies are 36,780 and 36,100 cal. An interesting feature of the reaction is that the reduction of mercuric chloride does not proceed to completion. The maximum reduction at 60° is about 40%.

Influence of Concentrations of Reactants

Table II records the results of six sets of experiments showing the influence of concentration of the reactants on the values of zero-order velocity constant. In each set the concentrations of two reactants were kept equal to 0.02 M, and the third was varied as noted in the columns.

TABLE II
Temperature = 50°.

t.	$(K_2S_2O_8)_0 = (HgCl_2)_0 = 0.02M.$ With $(H_2C_2O_4)_0$		$(K_2S_2O_8)_0 = (H_2C_2O_4)_0 = 0.02M.$ With $(HgCl_2)_0$		$(H_2C_2O_4)_0 = (HgCl_2)_0 = 0.02M.$ With $(K_2S_2O_8)_0$	
	$k_0 \times 10^3$		$k_0 \times 10^3$		$k_0 \times 10^3$	
	0.04 M.	0.08 M.	0.04 M.	0.08 M.	0.04 M.	0.08 M.
0 min.	..	..	..	..	..	..
60	11.66	13.33	13.33	21.66	13.33	20.00
120	10.00	10.00	13.33	20.00	25.00	26.66
180	10.00	11.66	12.50	21.66	35.00	-1.66
240	10.00	11.66	15.83	26.66	3.33	-1.66
300	16.66	33.33	21.66	38.33	-1.66	-1.66

From Tables I and II it is observed that the zero-order velocity constant is not appreciably affected by increasing the concentration of oxalic acid. This suggests that the order of the reaction with respect to oxalic acid is zero. It also appears that k_0 increases with increase in the concentration of mercuric chloride. The order of the reaction with respect to mercuric chloride, calculated from the data of these tables by the differential method, is found to change from 0.5 to 1.0 with the progress of the reaction. By increasing the concentration of potassium persulphate, the zero-order velocity constant does not show constancy as the reaction becomes auto-catalytic sooner, but auto-inhibition and reversibility set in earlier. Hence, it is difficult to assign any definite order of the reaction with respect to potassium persulphate. The maximum reduction of mercuric chloride decreases by increasing the concentration of persulphate.

Influence of Nitrogen

To study the influence of nitrogen on the reduction of mercuric chloride, nitrogen gas was bubbled through the reaction mixture at a uniform rate. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

 $(K_2S_2O_8)_0 = (H_2C_2O_4)_0 = (HgCl_2)_0 = 0.02 M.$ Temp. = 50°.

	Volume of KIO_3 .	Average C.	$k_0 \times 10^6$.
0 min.	0.0 c.c.	20.0	--
30	2.0	19.0	66.666
60	4.0	17.0	66.666
120	8.8	13.6	80.000
180	9.6	10.8	13.333
240	9.3	16.6	-5.000

Comparing Table III with Table I, it may be seen that nitrogen exerts an accelerating influence on the velocity of formation of mercurous chloride. The reduction of mercuric chloride reaches up to about 56%.

Influence of Sodium Acetate

The reduction of mercuric chloride was studied at 40°, 50° and 60° in presence of two different concentrations of sodium acetate, keeping the concentration of each of the reactants and the inductor equal to 0.02 M. The results obtained are represented in Fig. 2. On comparing it with Fig. 1, it is observed that in presence of 0.1 M sodium acetate, the period of normal velocity at 50° and 60° decreases with increase of temperature and auto-catalysis, followed by auto-inhibition, set

FIG. 2

in earlier. However, reversibility of the reaction is not observed and the overall reaction is much faster than that without sodium acetate. The reduction of mercuric chloride goes to almost completion in one hour at 60°. It is further noted that on increasing the concentration of the acetate to 1.0 M, the velocity of reduction of mercuric chloride is suppressed, but yet remains higher than that without the acetate (cf. Figs. 1 & 2). It is interesting to note that in presence of 0.1 M sodium acetate, the period of induction observed is much less than that without it, but when the concentration of the acetate is 1.0 M, this period becomes larger than that when no sodium acetate is used.

DISCUSSION

Investigation of the kinetics of the reduction of mercuric chloride reveals that the reaction develops through various zones and may be governed by a chain mechanism as shown below :

Chain breaking processes :—

The period of induction is the time required for the thermal activation of the $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ ion so as to break into SO_4^- radicals which produce CO_2^- radicals responsible for the reduction of mercuric chloride.

The decrease in the period of induction in presence of 0.1 M sodium acetate is due to the reduction in the concentration of H^+ ions of the acid which exert an inhibiting influence on the reduction of mercuric chloride, possibly due to their catalysing influence on step (7) :

with the result that the velocity of production of CO_2^- radical by SO_4^- (step 2) is suppressed. When the concentration of the acetate is 1.0 M, i.e., it is in large excess compared to that of oxalic acid, it may also exert a kinetic salt effect causing decrease in the velocity of reduction (Fig. 2).

According to the above mechanism, the reduction of mercuric chloride (or the precipitation of mercurous chloride) is governed by step (4). By employing the usual steady state approximations

for the various radicals, the velocity of formation of mercurous chloride may be expressed by the equation :

$$\frac{d[\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2]}{dt} = k \frac{C_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}} \cdot C_{\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}} \cdot C_{\text{Hg}^{2+}}}{C_{\text{O}_2} \left[1 + k' \frac{C_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}}}{C_{\text{O}_2}} \right]} \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

where k and k' are constants.

Equation (13) demands that the velocity of reduction of mercuric chloride should increase by increasing the concentration of oxalic acid or mercuric chloride. Since step (7) is very slow, the concentration of dissolved oxygen may be assumed to be proportional to the volume of the reaction mixture, which is kept constant for each observation. It has been observed that oxygen exerts a very strong inhibiting influence on the reduction. Hence, on increasing the concentration of the persulphate within low values, when the ratio $C_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}}/C_{\text{O}_2}$ is small compared to unity, the velocity of reduction of mercuric chloride should increase, but at higher concentrations of it, when the ratio increases appreciably, the velocity of reduction should decrease. These observations are supported by data in Tables I and II.

The zero-order, exhibited by the reaction in the early stage, is due to steps (4), (5) and (6). The concentration of CO_2^- is maintained constant by steps (4) and (5), and as soon as it is formed it reacts with Hg^{2+} ion irrespective of its (Hg^{2+}) concentration, and hence, exhibits zero-order. The auto-catalysis after the period of normal velocity is due to the increase in the concentration of SO_4^- radical and consequently in the rate of production of CO_2^- radical by step (2), resulting in the increased velocity of reduction of mercuric chloride by step (4), which is faster than step (3). The increase in velocity continues up to a limiting value when the chain-breaking processes (7) to (10) develop and cause inhibition in the reaction. The reversibility in the reaction (i.e. the decrease in the amount of precipitated mercurous chloride) in the last stages is due to the action of molecular oxygen produced in step (8) on mercurous ion, as explained below :

The accelerating influence of nitrogen is due to the removal of some of the dissolved oxygen from the reaction mixture and decreases its inhibiting influence. The H^- ions destroy SO_4^- radical which produces the CO_2^- radical. Sodium acetate removes H^+ ions and stabilises SO_4^- radical with the result that the chains are elongated and reduction of mercuric chloride reaches to almost completion (Fig. 2). When the concentration of the acetate is in large excess compared to that of the acid, e.g. 1.0 M, a fraction of it reacts with H^+ ions and the rest exerts kinetic salt effect on the velocity of reduction of mercuric chloride (Fig. 2).

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